

Successive Partition Method for Binomial Coefficient in Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the successive partition method applied to a binomial coefficient in combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-13]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-13] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem 2.1: $V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!}$ where $n, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$.

Proof. $\binom{n+r}{n} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!(n+r-n)!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+r)}{r!}$.

Here, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+r)}{r!} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{n+i}{r!}$.

From the above expressions, we conclude that

$$V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!}, \text{ where } n, r \geq 0 \ \& \ n, r \in N.$$

Theorem 2.2: $V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}$, ($n, r \geq 1 \ \& \ n, r \in N$).

Proof. Let us apply Theorem 2.1 to the binomial identity as follows:

$$= \frac{(n+r-1)!}{n!(r-1)!} + \frac{(r+n-1)!}{r!(n-1)!}, \quad \text{where } (n+r-1) = (r+n-1).$$

$$\text{So, } V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = (n+r-1)! \left(\frac{1}{n!(r-1)!} + \frac{1}{r!(n-1)!} \right).$$

By simplifying this expression, we get

$$V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = (n+r-1)! \left(\frac{r}{n!r!!} + \frac{n}{r!n!} \right) = \frac{(n+r-1)!(r+n)}{n!r!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = V_n^r.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Successive Partition Method

The successive partitions applied to a binomial coefficient (root) V_n^r are given below:

$$V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}.$$

$$V_n^r = (V_n^{r-2} + V_{r-1}^{n-1}) + (V_r^{n-2} + V_{n-1}^{r-1}).$$

$$V_n^r = (V_n^{r-3} + V_{r-2}^{n-1}) + (V_{r-1}^{n-2} + V_{n-2}^{r-1}) + (V_r^{n-3} + V_{n-2}^{r-1}) + (V_{n-1}^{r-2} + V_{r-1}^{n-2}).$$

Similarly, we can partition each item into sum of two parts again and again.

The final binomial coefficient (leaf) under the successive partitions of V_n^r (root) is given below:

$$V_{r-k}^{n-n} \text{ or } V_{n-k}^{r-r}, \quad (n-k \geq 1 \ \& \ r-k \geq 1).$$

The binomial coefficients between root and leafs are named as predecessors and successors.

Also, we can show these root, predecessors, successors, and leafs in a tree diagram.

4. Conclusion

In this article, successive partition method was applied to a binomial coefficient in combinatorial geometric series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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